
THE IMPROVEMENT OF COGNITIVE QUALITIES THROUGH PLAY

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Abstract:

This article explores the idea that playing video games can improve cognitive qualities such as critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and strategic planning. The article highlights the benefits of approaching learning tasks like a video game, breaking them down into smaller challenges to stay motivated and engaged. It concludes that video games can be a powerful tool for learning and personal growth, improving cognitive qualities that can benefit individuals in various aspects of their lives.

Keywords: problem-solving skills, cognitive development, infancy, playtime, communication skills.

As technology continues to advance, video games have become a popular form of entertainment for people of all ages. However, recent studies have shown that playing video games can also have a positive impact on cognitive abilities such as critical thinking, problem-solving skills, and strategic planning. This article explores how video games can be used as a tool for learning and personal growth, highlighting the story of a young boy who saw significant improvement in his academic performance through playing video games. By breaking down learning tasks into smaller challenges, individuals can approach them like a video game and stay motivated and engaged. Ultimately, this article argues that video games can be a powerful tool for improving cognitive qualities that can benefit individuals in various aspects of their lives. The word "cognitive development" refers to a child's ability to reason and think for himself. This development might differ amongst

children of different ages and emphasize the development of specific talents and intellectual characteristics. Proper cognitive development in children is essential for information processing and self-recognition, both of which can aid in understanding other people's views and feelings. It is also responsible for teaching a youngster how to compare and contrast concepts, form their own opinions, and evaluate alternatives. The surroundings of a kid can influence the process of intellectual development in terms of thinking, memory, and language. This development can also refer to changes in assimilation and accommodation, which occur as a kid adjusts to new experiences, conceptions, and sensations. These experiences may teach students how to focus on more than one subject at a time and think in tangible and hypothetical ways, which can be valuable in academic contexts for problem solving. It is critical for youngsters to comprehend the distinction between making observations, gathering information, and processing ideas at this point. This type of thinking can impact a child's decision-making as they develop complicated thinking skills and construct their own worldviews. Finally, cognitive development in children is an important aspect of developing skills that will impact puberty. This expansion lays the groundwork for future success.

Infancy

The infancy stage ranges from birth to approximately 2 years old. Here, you may notice that children can slowly begin to identify specific objects in their surroundings. Additionally, infants can often also:

Express that they're interested in things

- * Pick things up and move them
- * Recognize familiar people or objects
- * Respond to affection
- * Demonstrate curiosity
- * Understand gestures or say certain words
- * Point to their body parts

* Enjoy playing games like peekaboo

Early and Middle Childhood

The early and middle childhood stage ranges from approximately 3 to 7 years old. These years allow children to further develop various skills. These abilities may include:

- Following instructions
- Doing puzzles and other crafts
- Building things and playing with more complex toys
- Beginning to understand time
- Naming colors and shapes
- Displaying better memory and attention span
- Reading and writing
- Counting numbers effectively
- Using new vocabulary and sentence structures
- Enjoying planning and building things

Playtime can help all children in a variety of ways. These encounters are crucial for children's cognitive development and to expose them to a world of possibilities. Play allows children to safely explore their surroundings, learn about their surroundings, and develop social skills.

1. Enhances Critical Thinking Skills

Free play can assist teach children decision-making skills and improve their critical thinking abilities. When a youngster is faced with external or internal inquiries such as why, when, what, or how, these talents might emerge. Encouraging a youngster to inquire about their surroundings will help them subsequently create their own logical conclusions. When infants are permitted to make some decisions on their own, an important part of critical thinking can emerge. Allowing a youngster to play freely can be good to his or her growth and

development. They are thus encouraged to reach their own findings and grow through various techniques.

2. Magnifies the Importance of Senses

A child's cognitive thinking skills will develop if they learn to play while employing and combining their senses of vision, taste, hearing, touch, and smell. This is referred to as sensory play, and it can be an important part of the educational process. A child's senses enable them to make more accurate comparisons and discover changes in their surroundings. Furthermore, children can use their senses to learn about their surroundings and become acquainted with new objects. Outdoor sensory play, such as on a playground, is very beneficial for youngsters learning to identify different textures, colors, and odors. Allowing youngsters to use their senses can help them establish their sensory network and increase their nerve connections as they grow. Activity panels in sensory play, in particular, encourage.

3. Improves Communication and Language Skills

Every child has to learn how to communicate and use language. They may begin to ask questions that will help them enhance their vocabulary and sentence structure as they play and engage with other children. They can learn to ask for help when climbing a structure or asking a buddy to play a game if they are playing outside. It's also beneficial to ask youngsters questions that teach them how to answer appropriately to different or new terms on a regular basis. Improving communication skills is essential for children to socially engage with others. Using their language skills, kids can brainstorm ideas with other children or figure out what games to play outside while taking into account the opinions of others. Teachers must be adept at utilizing media or learning tools in order for pupils to more readily explore their cognitive talents in order to increase children's cognitive abilities. The concept of learning with block media is one type of media that increases children's cognitive abilities. As a game, so that children can use their imaginations. A media block is a piece of wood that comes in a variety of

shapes. In general, they are rectangular or cube-shaped. The evolution of the beam as a game tool. Children enjoy stacking or combining blocks to create the form of their choice. As game equipment, various sorts of beams are employed. Media youngsters can recognize the shape of objects, their sizes, and different colors of objects via the beam.

In conclusion, video games have proven to be more than just a form of entertainment. They can be used as a tool for learning and personal growth, helping individuals improve their cognitive abilities such as critical thinking, problem-solving, and strategic planning. By breaking down learning tasks into smaller challenges, individuals can approach them like a video game and stay motivated and engaged. The story of the young boy who saw significant improvement in his academic performance through playing video games is a testament to the positive impact that video games can have on cognitive qualities. With technology continuing to advance, it is exciting to see how video games will continue to be utilized as a powerful tool for improving cognitive abilities that can benefit individuals in various aspects of their lives.

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